

SHADOW RUNOFF THEORY, AN ENGINEERING DESIGN APPROACH TO IMPACT CONTROL OF MINE RUNOFF ON TSS CONCENTRATION AND SEDIMENTATION

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Abstract: *An open mining system that uses a selective method is a system commonly used for the retrieval of mineral materials as is commonly done in nickel mining. This mining system resulted in extensive land clearing. If not accompanied by reclamation and revegetation actions, it will cause problems to the environment, especially for the physical environmental components of the chemical erosion and sedimentation, one of which is the increase of TSS concentration. Shadow runoff is "environmental friendly", no chemical, low cost and easy maintenance, but must pay close attention to potential safety risks when the work activity is done. This research tested shadow runoff hypothesis, with approach of hydrological science, oceanography, and fluid mechanics can decrease TSS concentration in pond at mining industry using open pit method. shadow runoff theory using a simple method that is by understanding the characteristics of water flow energy, be it surface flow or turbulent flow in water or commonly referred to as water flow patterns. This method applies the natural process of mixing flow in the fjord-type estuary zone combined with the fluid flow mechanism. This theory is then tested with field experiment and statistics using the autocorrelation test. Where there is a positive autocorrelation between rainfall and TSS concentration after shadow runoff applied. There are two benefits that can be obtained by using shadow runoff on erosion and sedimentation problems, as a dilution pond and a sediment pond. Significantly shadow runoff shows when rainfall is high then TSS concentration will decrease. This condition applies when the pond serves as a diluent pond. The function as a sedimentary pond is able to reduce the sediment load out of the maximum outlet by 8 percent.*

Key words: Total Suspended Solid (TSS), Shadow Runoff Theory, Sediment Pond.

Introduction

In mining activities carried out, techniques used to take ore reserves using selective mining techniques. In the AMDAL (EIA) study and other research on study mining areas, the majority of land types are dominated by laterite soil types. Although previous studies have recommended environmental management and management techniques for important impacts, there is no possibility for additional research studies to be applied directly in the field. The results of the evaluation of the significant impacts occurring and looking directly at the conditions occurring in the field, in particular the environmental components of physical-chemical properties, on the management of erosion and sedimentation and the rate of surface flow, an additional theoretical engineering approach to address the problem.

Key Questions

- How to approach the best engineering design, so the problem of increasing TSS concentration can be reduced.
- How much the maximum sediment volume that can be accommodated using the engineering design approach.

Literature Review

The working area of this study shows that the geomorphological conditions have a low to medium wavy hill type. Rolling hills with a slope of 5° - 30° with southeast orientation. This unit is composed of laterite soil, gravel and saprolite blocks and located at elevations of 50-100 meters above sea level. Lateritization on this morphology based on the slope of the slope indicates medium-high weathering process. The result of this erosion process is covering soil and thick

and wide laterite deposit. (PT.Reka Bumi, 2017). The TSS concentration was determined using a filtration method. Porcelain crucible was oven dried at 103^o C to remove all the water vapours. The mass of the porcelain crucible plus a glass fibre filter with pore size of 0.6 µm were weighed using 4 digits analytical balance. The TSS concentration was calculated by taking the difference between the total mass of dried porcelain crucible, a fibre filter and its filtrate and the empty dried porcelain crucible and its fibre filter over the volume of river water samples of 25 mL. (Daphne, Low Hui Xiang, Handojo Djati Utomo, and Lim Zhi Hao Kenneth, 2011). Clay and sludge particles have electro-magnetic properties that bind hybrid grains together to give mass or mass cohesion (CIRIA 1996). This process is called "Flocculation" which occurs when the dispersed colloidal phase (ie sludge) forms discrete particles that can precipitate from the dispersion medium (ie water). (Mohamed A. Abdelrhman. 2016). Settle rate for erosion and deposit of cohesive and non cohesive particles, the treatment is different. Particles of cohesive aggregates to form larger particles with higher precipitation speeds will pull particles out of the water column, reduce turbidity, and increase the clarity of water. This process is the result of electrical charges on the surface of cohesive particles (clay and sludge). (Mohamed A. Abdelrhman. 2016). Short rain may not cause runoff, but rain with the same intensity and longer will cause surface runoff. Thus the total surface flow for a rain event is related to the duration of the rain with a certain intensity. (Irwan Sukri Banuwa, 2013). The runoff is responsible for causing erosion, as this runoff will transport the soil and parts of the soil from the higher to the lower area. (Irwan Sukri Banuwa, 2013). Sediment yield is the total number of particles (suspended or bedload) that reach outlets from the drainage of the river over a period of time. The amount of transport flow/sediment delivery is usually expressed as kilograms per square kilometer per year. The process of sediment delivery is influenced by many factors such as the size of the drainage area, the slope of the basin, the climate, the type of sediment (lithology), the vegetation cover, and the practice of human land use/management. The theoretical concept of 'Sediment Delivery Ratio' (ratio between yield and total amount of eroded sediments) illustrates the fact that not all deposits are eroded in a particular catch area that reaches the sewer (because, for example, deposition in the floodplain). Such storage opportunities usually increase in larger size catches, resulting in a lower sediment delivery ratio. (Marangu PK, Mwenda E and Theuri DM. 2016).

In addition, also a problem is the presence of sedimentation in the downstream area. Where the total sediment transported from upstream to downstream is expressed in units of volume over a period of time. The total amount of this sediment (sediment yield) refers to the inorganic fraction in the sediment regardless of the organic material transported. (MacGregor K. 2011). The problem of transition to turbulence has now been studied formally for over 100 years. Despite this, one of the very few things upon which all research workers agree is that the issue is a complex and difficult one. At the present time, there is no general theory of transition - nor are we even close to developing one. Consequently, an important philosophical gap exists between those who perform theoretical work and those who have to produce estimates for transition to be used in engineering design. This has resulted in a dual and largely unrelated approach to the problem. As a rather general statement, the theoreticians (and the experimental scientists) have concentrated on trying to understand transition in certain types of very simple flows where the number of variables is reduced to the absolute minimum. Examples of those which have been studied are flat-plate flow, pipe and channel flow and flow over simple shapes such as cones. Extensive work has revealed that, even though the shapes may be simple, the physics of the transition process is always complex. The consequence of this has been that all attempts to predict the details of transition - usually through stability theory (not transition theory) or, occasionally, turbulence modeling (not strictly a theoretical approach) have required a detailed and accurate description of the basic flow upon which a very large number of computations need to be performed. This approach is of little use in an industrial design process where candidate configurations may be changed repeatedly in an attempt to find a solution which satisfies a very large number of absolute constraints. The implications of shape change must be assessed rapidly and, particularly in the early stages, an extensive knowledge of detail and a high level of accuracy are not always needed. Consequently, the "industrial" approach has been to produce simple estimation techniques based upon correlations of data from wind-tunnel tests and, whenever possible, from flight using overall characteristics such as length Reynolds

number, freestream Mach number, incidence configuration-specific correlations. (Poll, D. I. "Laminar-turbulent transition." *AGARD Advisory Report 319*, 1996). Fjord-shaped estuary, the profile of the valley U-shaped. Like the Drowned river valley, this estuary fjord is also found in temperate regions and formed by melting of icebergs (glaciers) during the Pleistocene. At the mouth of the estuary there is usually a sill (valley plateau sticking out), so the waters in that section are quite shallow. While the depth of the valley (water basin) under a very deep sill, can reach about 300-400 m, some even reach 800 m. the freshwater input from the river is relatively large compared to the volume of sea water when the tide, while the outflow of the river compared with the total volume of the fjord is relatively small (Dedy Kurniawan. 2010).

Methodology

This research uses quantitative methods (postpositivist claims) and uses the method of sampling purposive random sampling.

Framework

Unlike the case with maintenance which has been done. The maintenance activities performed regular routine dredging is known volume of sludge issued. While in the normalization of activities include the making/design changes that exist to achieve maximum results of an problem object. There are 3 (three) ponds at the study location, where all three ponds are covered in thick sludge that has not been maintained for several years. So that the runoff water from upstream to study location as its downstream becomes the main problem, either from the quality factor or the quantity of runoff. The engineering design for ponds normalization is scaled up or focused on decreasing TSS concentration in ponds capacity with a certain capacity.

Shadow Runoff Theory – State of Art

"The surface flow rate will be inhibited by its flow rate by breaking the water energy when passing through the drop structure (sr1), then divided into two streams flow. Where, there is a straight stream (sr2) and also there is a deflected (sr3). This deflected flow, then backflows due to the depth contours at the ends is made higher. In addition there is also a narrow angle factor at the end of the drainage channel (slope), so that when the flow end the slope, there was a transition of laminar water flow into turbulent flow. The faster the speed of the surface flow, it will encourage the flow turbulence process under the surface flow. Before the process of turbulence in water, then first the flowing water undergoes a process of precipitation by gravity."

Figure 01: The Principle Engineering Design (Shadow runoff) Drainage Channel Ponds

Figure 02: Longitudinal Slope Shadow Runoff Technical Design

Slope stability analysis report

Infinite Slope v. 3.0

GENERAL INFO

Project title: Shadow Raunoff
 File path and name: D:\Shadow Runoff.ins
 Printing date and time: 31/01/2018 10:27:31

INPUT DATA

Geometry

Inclination of the slope: $\alpha = 11,3^\circ$
 Depth of bedrock: $Z_{bed} = 5,00$ m
 Depth of groundwater free surface: $Z_w = 0,00$ m

Soil properties

Cohesion: $c' = 10$ kPa
 Angle of shear strength: $\phi' = 25,0^\circ$
 Porosity: $n = 0,38$ -
 Unit weight of soil particles: $\gamma_s = 27,00$ kN/m³
 Unit weight of the soil above groundwater surface: $\gamma = 20,47$ kN/m³
 Saturated unit weight (below groundwater surface): $\gamma_{sat} = 20,47$ kN/m³
 Effective unit weight of the soil: $\gamma' = 10,66$ kN/m³
 Unit weight of water: $\gamma_w = 9,81$ kN/m³

Pore water pressures

Type of groundwater: slope fully submerged ()

ANALYSIS

Settings

Type of calculation: evaluation of the (minimum) factor of safety
 Seismic condition: no
 Minimum allowable factor of safety: $F_{safe} = 1,300$ -

Slice forces

Weight of soil (eventual buoyancy force is computed): $W' = 53,29$ kN/m
 Normal effective force: $N' = 52,26$ kN/m
 Mobilized shear force at the base: $T_{mob} = 10,43$ kN/m
 Shear strength at the base: $T_f = 34,56$ kN/m

Current stability assessment

Safety factor of the slope: $F = 3,315$ -
 Depth of the critical slip surface: $Z_{crit} = 5,00$ m
 Stability assessment: SLOPE IS STABLE AND SAFE

DESIGN LINEOUTS

Drainage trenches (Hutchinson, 1977)

Width of the trenches: $B_{tren} = 1,0$ m
 Depth or height of the trenches: $H_{tren} = 10,0$ m
 Spacing between trenches: $D_{tren} = 5,0$ m
 Position of the impervious surface: $Z_{imp} \gg H_{tren}$
 Final depth of the groundwater surface: $Z_w^* = 0,00$ m
 Efficiency of the system of trenches: $E = 86$ %

Final stability assessment

Final factor of safety of the slope: $F^* = 3,315$ -
 Final depth of critical slip surface: $Z_{crit}^* = 5,00$ m

Simple Calculation of Ponds Water Capacity

A simple calculation is done by calculation approach in the work area image map (google map). While this is less accurate, it can provide the basic information needed for the research.

Figure 03: Simple Calculation Approach Ponds Water Capacity

Ponds was originally designed to accommodate runoff or sediment yield from upstream sources. Large ponds have been created to anticipate the impact. But the construction of the pond does not pay attention to routine maintenance on a regular basis that will be done. The extent of the pond makes it difficult for long arm PC 200 excavator to reach the thick sludge surface. This condition is particularly noticeable in pond 3. When the rain falls, the upstream water carrying the sediment will continue to flow unhindered to the pond outlet. This is because the sludge level was almost close to the outlet of pond. In pond 2, some of the surface is rather hard allowing long arm excavators to descend into the pond and sludge dredging. Nevertheless it remains to be considered the water flow plan that will be made. This is intended to anticipate when the rainfall in high intensity with water discharge is also high. While in pond 1, has a layer of sediment that is not thick. So the ground base is easily found at a depth of ± 0,5 meters.

Trend of Rainfall Evaluation and TSS Concentration

Based on the graph of Fig. 3, there is a significant improvement pattern between rainfall and TSS concentration. Rainfall is directly proportional to the concentration of TSS, whereas when large rainfall will be followed also the TSS concentration is also increased. This indicates ponds is not working properly. In other words, ponds is merely a place through which runoff water flows from upstream to downstream.

Figure 03: Trend Evaluation of Rainfall and TSS Concentration December 2017

Table 01: Rainfall and Concentration Data of Ponds, December 2017

Date	Rainfall (mm)	Rainfall Volume (m3)	TSS (mg/l)
01-Des-17	6,4	1.580	0,0
02-Des-17	0,0	-	48
03-Des-17	20,2	4.990	236
04-Des-17	0,0	-	0,0
05-Des-17	0,0	-	4,4
06-Des-17	0,0	-	0,0
07-Des-17	0,0	-	17,8
08-Des-17	0,2	0,05	22,4
09-Des-17	18,8	4.640	65,6
10-Des-17	8,6	2.120	328
11-Des-17	0,6	0,15	10,8
12-Des-17	0,0	-	8,8

Source: Primary Data, Swapantau Enviro Section Laboratory, December 2017

The experimental steps are:

First Phase

Pond 3 construction

Calculation estimation :

1. 74.51 m x 7 m = 521,27 (Drainage Channel 1)
2. 102.,84 m x 5 m = 514,2 (Drainage Channel 2)
3. 73.38 m x 7 m = 513,66 (Drainage Channel 3)

Figure 4. Construction Design of Shadow

Shadow Runoff Theory is applied in drainage channel 3.

While drainage 1 and drainage 2 drainage only done regular dredging as thick as 5 meter. So it can be calculated the maximum capacity or capacity of drainage channels to accommodate water in pond 3 is as follows: $(1+2+3)*5 = 1.549,13*5 = 7.745,65 \text{ m}^3$

Second Phase

Pond 2 construction

Calculation estimation :

1. 73.25 m x 7 m = 521,27 (Drainage Channel4)
2. 42.,14 m x 5 m = 294,98 (Drainage Channel5)
3. 67.23 m x 7 m = 470,61 (Drainage Channel6)

Shadow Runoff application is applied in drainage channel 6. While drainage channel 4 and 5 only done regular dredging as thick as 5 meter. So it can be calculated maximum capacity or drainage capacity to accommodate water in pond 2 is as follows: $(1+2+3)*5 = 1.278,34*5 = 6.392 \text{ m}^3$

Shadow Runoff

Figure 5. Sketch of Shadow Runoff Design

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experiment Pond 3

Pond 3 have water reserve is $7,745.65 \text{ m}^3$, after 1 x 24 hours this water reserve will be stable or gravity precipitation has occurred and become "diluent" when the runoff of upstream water is introduced. The steady pace of the settling process is due to the cohesive enegery of clay or mud that accelerates the flocculation process in water. Visually, the water condition changes color from brown (*turbid*) to become greenish. Of course, the capacity of dilution power by using the runoff shadow theory has a certain limit so that it can work effectively in accordance with the maximum capacity of the pond. This experiment begins on December 14, 2017 (See Figure 4). On December 18, 2017, there was heavy rain with 15.2 mm rainfall causing an increase in TSS concentration of 174 mg/l (still below the water quality standard). Until December 23, 2017 there is no rainfall. Nevertheless the flow remains out at pond outlet with low discharge. Below is the rainfall data and TSS concentration during the first phase of the experiment.

Table 02: Rainfall Data and Concentration Pond 3 December 2017 (Construction Phase)

Date	Rainfall (mm)	Rainfall Volume (m3)	TSS (mg/l)
17-Dec-17	3,0	0,741	0,0
18-Dec-17	15,2	3.754	174
19-Dec-17	0,0	0	8,8
20-Dec-17	10,2	2.519	0,0
21-Dec-17	0,4	0,099	0,0
22-Dec-17	5,8	1.432	5,6
23-Dec-17	0,0	0	2,8

Source: Primary Data, Swapantau Enviro Section Laboratory, December 2017.

The concentration of TSS in pond is 2.8 mg/l, which is the lowest TSS concentration during the last month. This shows, there is a significant process of gravity and the constructions of drainage channel shadow runoff optimally.

Figure 06: Rainfall correlation and TSS concentration after the shadow runoff experiment

From Figure 6 above, after the shadow runoff experiment has been completed, the correlation pattern is directly proportional to rainfall and TSS concentration. If there is an increase in rainfall, it will be followed by a decrease in TSS concentration. January 1, 2018, the outlet does not necessarily become turbid, thus increasing the concentration of TSS. It is seen on the morning of January 2, 2018, the condition of outlet pond 3 still looks clear, although it looks a little bit colorful. In pond 2 itself, the water becomes turbid due to sediment yield from upstream. The concentration of TSS can not be known because sampling is done in the afternoon, and pond 3 outlet is not flowing water (No Discharge). This occurred again on January 3, 2018, again the rain fell rapidly and long enough where the date of January 4, 2018, is known from the analysis of TSS concentration of 6.80 mg / l.

The concentration of TSS in ponds is 2.8 mg/l, which is the lowest TSS concentration during the last month. This shows, there is a significant process of gravity and the constructions of drainage channel shadow runoff optimally. It can be seen the function of shadow runoff has a positive autocorrelation of rainfall and TSS concentration.

Experiment Pond 2

The work continued for the second phase, the experimental pond 2. During the 40% construction period there have been two rains with significant rain intensity. Likewise, on Saturday afternoon the rainy season is quite heavy and the TSS concentration value is 1.20 mg/l (See Figure 7.). This TSS value is the lowest during the shadow runoff design development experiment on ponds 2 and 3.

Two days later, the concentration of TSS continues to increase, while the rainfall is decreased, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 07: TSS Concentration at Pond 3 First Week 2018

The correlation pattern of precipitation with TSS concentration is inversely proportional. Where, there is an increase in TSS concentration when there is decreased rainfall. This is because the design of shadow runoff construction is not suitable that done in the field. Technical misinformation occurs, where drainage channeling is done by making sediment trap that lead directly from the drainage channel source. In the event of high rainfall with high intensity, the drainage channel will potentially function as a "By Pass" from upstream. While the drainage channel corresponding to the initial design on its inlet is closed, so it can not enter the water from upstream, from 7 to 10 January 2018. This theory takes from the actual error conditions in the field, drainage channels that do not fit this initial design as a real shadow runoff drainage. Thus, the initial design theory used is called Shadow Runoff. To control the error that occurred, then on January 11, 2018 opened the drainage channel that leads back shadow runoff. While drainage channels leading into sediment trap are intentionally not closed back for use as control of theoretical argument "By Pass". There has been rainfall with long intensity for three consecutive, ie, from January 13 to 15, 2018. This rainfall causes runoff from upstream overflow and inundate pond 2 and pond 3 with a large enough capacity, which impacts TSS drastic increase and extreme. Pond 3 capacity in the second phase of the shadow runoff construction design can not accommodate such a large runoff flow. The following rainfall data and TSS concentration for three days.

Table 03: Rainfall Data and TSS Concentration January 2018

Date	Rainfall (mm)	Rainfall Volume (m3)	TSS (mg/l)
12-Jan-18	0,4	0,099	2,0
13-Jan-18	67,6	16.697	1.720
14-Jan-18	57,4	14.178	14.552
15-Jan-18	2,8	0,691	1.672
16-Jan-18	0,0		16.808
17-Jan-18	0,0		3.520
18-Jan-18	0,0		7.092

Source: Primary Data, Swapantau Enviro Section Laboratory, January 2018.

Based on the data in Table 3, the maximum runoff volume that occurred was on 13 January at 16,697 m³. Theoretically, the sediment trap serve as a settling pond, where when the first pond is filled with water, it will flow into the next sediment trap without any turbulence mechanism inside. So the mixing process for dilution does not occur. Besides, it is also the time factor of the run-off for running the process too close. The prediction for sediment traps made as "By Pass" of runoff water from upstream proved after a sufficient intensive rainfall for 4 days resulting in the function of ponds 2 and 3 as a diluent material switching function into sedimentary sediment ponds. Where from a safety point of view this is a potential risk that can unsafe the maintenance activity of the pond. Rainfall is directly proportional to the concentration of TSS, whereas when large rainfall will be followed also the TSS concentration is also increased. This indicates ponds is not working properly. In other words, ponds is merely a place

through which runoff water flows from upstream to downstream. An autocorrelation test was conducted between rainfall and concentration in September, October, and early December 2017, which for November was not due to only 4 days of rainy days and no outflow at pond outlet. Followed by autocorrelation graph display during shadow runoff experiment on ponds. (Figure 8).

Figure 08: Autocorrelation test of precipitation and TSS concentration before and after shadow runoff

Calculation of Analysis of Diluent and Settling Ponds

Based on data from Tables 2 and 3 can be calculated as follows:

Total maximum water capacity of pond 2 and pond 3 are:

- Pond 2 $(1+2+3)*5 = 1.278,34*5 = 6.391,7 \text{ m}^3$ (1)
- Pond 3 $(1+2+3)*5 = 1.549,13*5 = 7.745,65 \text{ m}^3$ (2)
- $(1+2) = 14.137,35 \text{ m}^3$ (3)

The total maximum sediment capacity of pond 2 and pond 3 is:

- Pond 2 $(1+2+3)*5 = 1.278,34*4 = 5.113,36\text{m}^3$ (4)
- Pond 3 $(1+2+3)*5 = 1.549,13*4 = 6.971,09\text{m}^3$ (5)
- $(4+5) = 11.309,88\text{m}^3$ (6)
- Maximum rainfall volume = 16.697 m^3 (7)

The maximum capacity of the two ponds mentioned above (calculation number 3), it can be understood that this capacity can not accommodate runoff from upstream on January 13, 2018 which is equal to $16,697 \text{ m}^3$.

The volume of runoff and sediment discharged from outlet pond 3 can be calculated:

- Maximum Water capacity 14.137 m^3 (3)
- Maximum sediment capacity $11.309,88\text{m}^3$ (6)
- Maximum Rainfall volume 16.697 m^3 (7)

The maximum runoff water coming out of the outlet of pond 3 is:

$$(7)-(3) = 2.560 \text{ m}^3 \text{ (8)}$$

And for the maximum sediment load coming out of outlet pond 3 is equal to

$$(6)/(3) = 0,8 \text{ (9)}$$

$$(8)*(9) = 2.048 \text{ m}^3 \text{ (10)}$$

Conclusions and Suggestions

The shadow runoff theory approach to ponds sediment shows a significant decrease in TSS concentration, in which the water reservoir in the pond serves as a "diluent". In case of runoff exceeding pond capacity and water reserves unable to process dilution, shadowrunoff switches into a sediment storage pond. This proves the principle of work done, namely by using shadow runoff theory to work effectively and optimally on pond sediment. Shadow runoff is "environmental friendly", no chemical used, low cost and easy maintenance, but must pay close attention to potential safety risks when the work activity is done. Shadow runoff is effective when applied to flat topography type and laterite soil type. Routine maintenance is required to maintain the proper functioning of the shadow runoff theory. This engineering design approach can be a consideration for the handling of runoff having TSS high concentrations. Nevertheless, there is a need for further research taking into consideration the important variables other than the above which have been done to support and constructively correlate the shadow runoff theory.

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